

Hi, I'm Steffi from Swinburne University of Technology, and a Southeast Asia Research Academy member. If you are from Southeast Asia and currently employed by a company, can you help me with my survey questionnaire by scanning on the QR code or clicking on this link <https://form.jotform.com/231494703217454>? Thank you very much!

